

Influence of novel Cu(II) complex on the photosystem II photochemical activity of spinach

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The mechanism of action of a large group of modern agents used for weed control inhibits electron transfer in the light stage of photosynthesis at one or another site of the electron-transport chain. Impact of the novel [CuL₂]Br₂ complex (L = bis4H-1,3,5-triazino [2,1-b] benzothiazole-2-amine, 4-(2-imidazole)copper(II) bromide complex) on the activity of PSII membranes isolated from spinach were studied by of photosynthetic oxygen evolution as well as changes in the PSII chlorophyll fluorescence yield (F_V) related to photoreduction of the Q_A plastoquinone, the PSII primary quinone electron acceptor. We show that [CuL₂]Br₂ effectively inhibits PSII photochemical activity as revealed by suppression of both the characteristic PSII photoreactions with the same similar effectiveness. [CuL₂]Br₂ decreases F_M level exclusively at the expense of F_V; causes neither changes in the F₀ level nor the retardation of the photoinduced rise in F_M. Artificial electron donors do not cancel the inhibitory effect of [CuL₂]Br₂. It is likely that [CuL₂]Br₂, which is included somewhere on the donor side or between its components, inhibits and/or slows down natural electron donation and/or serves as an exogenous electron donor for RC. Thus, the PSII reaction center's components are most likely the major target of [CuL₂]Br₂ inhibitory activity. The data obtained are compared to the literature information concerning the inhibitory effects of Cu(II) aqua ions and Cu(II)-organic complexes on PSII.

Keywords: Photosynthetic inhibitors; copper; metalorganic complexes; photosystem II; oxygen evolution

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, new methods are being intensively developed and used in practice to selectively ensure the survival of economically significant (genetically modified) crops during treatment by modern chemical agents that effectively suppress the growth and development of undesirable plant species, which will provide a good agricultural economy (Ahmad et al., 2017). An important aspect of these methods is studying the mechanism of action of the widest possible spectrum and the largest number of different chemical agents - potential prototypes of new, more effective, more environmentally friendly, more bioremediated, etc. compounds that inhibit weed growth (Schütte et al., 2017).

In addition, these chemical agents under study may turn out to be new highly specific tools for science, acting as inhibitors of a certain activity, acceptors, or electron donors with special properties (Nelson et al., 2015). The scientific study already makes extensive use of numerous well-researched electron donors, acceptors, and inhibitors of photosynthetic electron transfer, for example, to isolate the desired section of the electron transfer chain of photosynthesis (Vass, 2012; Pospíšil et al., 2016) and even for practical purposes, for example, in modified natural systems to produce molecular hydrogen (Pospíšil et al., 2016; Zharmukhamedov et al., 2021)

Due to the power of the Sun, photosynthesis, which is a special trait of plant cells, guarantees the growth and development of plants. Photosystem II

(PSII), one of the main complexes of the photosynthetic apparatus (PA), splits water into electrons, protons and oxygen (Nelson et al., 2015). Among all PA complexes, PSII and its oxygen-evolving complex (OEC) are the sites of damage due to many stresses and agents (Vass, 2012), including the formation of reactive oxygen species (Pospíšil et al., 2016). It is possible to inhibit the action of any PA component to eliminate weeds without harming animals. But blocking PSII OEC, the most significant component of PA, is more efficient. The majority of pesticides, photosynthesis inhibitors, including urea derivatives, triazine, and phenolic inhibitors, operate in this manner (Zharmukhamedov et al., 2021).

There have been numerous efforts to create new inhibitory organic complexes in addition to the previously mentioned inhibitors of the photosynthetic electron transfer chain, particularly PSII (Semelkova et al., 2015; Gonec et al., 2017), complexes of organic ligands with semimetals (Sb, As, etc.) (Karacan et al., 2016) and transition metals (Fe, Pb, Co, Ni, Cr, Zn) (Karki et al., 2000; Santillo et al., 2014; Karacan et al., 2014) including organometallic complexes based on copper (Cu(II)) (Sersen et al., 1997; Rodionova et al., 2017).

The ability to control the availability of a metal to a particular site of action by altering a number of properties of such an agent by selecting the best ligand through the complexation of a metal with an organic ligand(s) can significantly increase the possibilities of using a metal ion as an inhibitor of biological activity (Garrido-Barros et al., 2017; Matheu et al., 2019). A metal can be complexed with a ligand (or ligands) to give the complex new, specialized properties that make it easier to create and maintain the required structure under various conditions, increase selectivity, and make it possible to easily coordinate with the target, all of which increase the overall effectiveness of inhibition (Matheu et al., 2019). The ligand(s) in the complex may be biologically active in addition to the metal, which raises the total activity of the organometallic complex. The ligand(s) may not be biologically active, but they secure or shield the chemically active metal from unwanted targets. However, metal continues to play a major part in the biological effects of organometallic complexes.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Thylakoids isolation

Thylakoids were isolated from the leaves of the greenhouse spinach (*Spinacia oleracea* L.) by using the method described previously (Berthold et al., 1981), and were suspended in a medium (A) containing 20 mM Mes–NaOH (pH 6.5), 0.33 M of

sucrose, 15 mM of NaCl, 10 mM of MgCl₂, and 10% glycerol and kept at –80°C.

2.2. PSII membranes isolation

From the leaves of the greenhouse spinach, the oxygen-evolving PSII-enriched thylakoid membrane fragments (PSII membranes) were isolated (*Spinacia oleracea* L.), as described earlier (Berthold et al., 1981). The PSII membranes were suspended in a medium (A) and were fast frozen for storage at –80 °C. 96% (v/v) ethanol was used to measure the overall chlorophyll concentration of the PSII membranes, as described earlier (Arnon, 1949).

2.3. Photosynthetic oxygen evolution measurements

The PSII membranes were used for measuring the rate of steady-state light-induced oxygen evolution under continuous saturating red light ($\lambda > 650$ nm, 1200 $\mu\text{mol photon s}^{-1} \text{m}^{-2}$), polarographically in Medium A at 25 °C by using a Clark-type Hansatech oxygen electrode (Hansatech Instruments Ltd., Norfolk, UK) connected to a water-temperature-controlled thermostat in the presence of a combination of two artificial electron acceptors: 100 μM of a strongly lipophilic dichloro-p-benzoquinone (DCBQ) dissolved in dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) and 1 mM potassium ferricyanide (FeCN) as additional electron acceptors to keep DCBQ in an oxidized state (Xiong et al., 1998). The PSII membrane concentration was equivalent to 20 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of chlorophyll.

2.4. Photoinduced changes of the psii chlorophyll fluorescence yield measurements

The photochemical activity of the PSII was also analyzed by measuring the kinetics of the light-induced changes of the PSII chlorophyll fluorescence yield (ΔF), associated with the photoreduction of the PSII primary electron acceptor, plastoquinone Q_A, with a pulse-amplitude modulation (PAM) fluorometer (XE-PAM, Heinz Walz, Germany) and accompanying software Power Graph Professional 3.3 in Medium A in a 10 mm cuvette at room temperature. The characteristic values F_V , F_0 , F_M , and the maximum quantum photochemical yield of PSII (ratio F_V/F_M), as well as the ratio F_V/F_0 , were determined. Here, F_0 is the fluorescence intensity before applying light, measured under weak light illumination, and F_M is the maximum fluorescence level, $F_V = F_M - F_0$, F_0 was recorded by using weak probe pulses of measuring light ($\lambda = 490$ nm; 4 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$; Xenon-Measuring Flash Lamp, 64 Hz, BG39, Schott). For the registration of the photoinduced changes in PSII chlorophyll fluorescence yield (F_V), the dark-adapted samples were illuminated by the light of saturating intensity ($\lambda = 490$ nm; 1000 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$, BG39, Schott).

Fig. 1. Tested ligand (4H-1,3,5-triazino [2,1-b]benzothiazole-2-amine,4-(2-imidazole)) (A) and Cu(II)-complex (Bis{4H-1,3,5-triazino [2,1-b]benzothiazole-2-amine,4-(2-imidazole)}copper(II) bromide) (B,C). (A,B), expanded structural formulas. (C), optimized molecular structures.

Fig. 2. Kinetics of oxygen release by PSII membranes in the absence of any additives (1) and in the presence of $[\text{CuL}_2]\text{Br}_2$ at a concentration of 3 μM (2); 20 μM (3); 50 μM (4); 100 μM (5). The reaction medium contained 50 mM MES (pH 6.5), 0.33 M sucrose, 15 mM NaCl, 0.1mM DCBQ, 1 mM FeCy. \uparrow and \downarrow – light ($\lambda = 650 \text{ nm}$, $1200 \mu\text{mol photon s}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2}$) on and off, respectively. Kinetics 6 was measured in the absence of artificial electron acceptors but in the presence of 30 μM $[\text{CuL}_2]\text{Br}_2$.

RESULTS

In this work was used $[\text{CuL}_2]\text{Br}_2$ complex. Ligand 4H-1,3,5-triazino [2,1-b]benzothiazole-2-amine,4-(2-imidazole) was synthesized for the first time by a condensation reaction between aldehydes (2-thiophenecarbaldehyde/2-imidazolecarbaldehyde) and 2-guanidobenzimidazole or 2-benzothiazole-guanidine.

$[\text{CuL}_2]\text{Br}_2$ was tested as an artificial electron acceptor for PSII in the photosynthetic oxygen release reaction. However, in the presence of only $[\text{CuL}_2]\text{Br}_2$ (from 1 μM to 30 μM) in the absence of

other artificial electron acceptors (AEA), oxygen release by PSII membranes was not observed, as shown in Fig. 2 (kinetics 6).

In the presence of AEA (DCBQ plus FeCy) without $[\text{CuL}_2]\text{Br}_2$ (control), PSII membranes under continuous illumination with saturated light generate oxygen at a rate of about $480 \mu\text{mol O}_2 (\text{mg Chl h})^{-1}$ (Fig. 2, kinetics 1). $[\text{CuL}_2]\text{Br}_2$ inhibits the release of oxygen depending on the concentration. At concentrations of 3 μM (2), 20 μM (3), 50 μM (4) and 100 μM , the reaction rate decreases by about 15%, 43%, 59% and 69% compared to the control (100%) (Fig. 1, kinetics 2-5).

Fig. 3. Kinetics of photoinduced changes in the fluorescence yield of chlorophyll PS II (ΔF) in the absence of any additives (kinetics 1) and in the presence of $[\text{CuL}_2]\text{Br}_2$ at a concentration of $8 \mu\text{M}$ (kinetics 2), $30 \mu\text{M}$ (kinetics 3) and $100 \mu\text{M}$ (kinetics 4). The triangle symbol indicates the moment of switching on the measuring light ($\lambda = 490 \text{ nm}$, $4 \text{ micromole photons m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$), exciting PSII chlorophyll fluorescence, F_0 ($\lambda \geq 650 \text{ nm}$). The up and down arrows indicate the moment corresponding to the switching on and off of the active light ($\lambda > 600 \text{ nm}$, $1000 \mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$).

Information about the localization of the site of inhibition of this inhibitor in PSII, about the possible mechanisms of action of the inhibitor can be obtained by using photoinduced changes of the PSII chlorophyll fluorescence yield associated with the photoreduction of the primary quinone-electron acceptor, Q_A , including the use of exogenous electron donors (acceptors) and/or known inhibitors with well-studied effects on PSII. The results of these studies are presented in Fig. 3.

In the presence of AEA (DCBQ plus FeCy) without $[\text{CuL}_2]\text{Br}_2$ (control), PSII membranes under continuous saturated light release oxygen at a rate of about $480 \mu\text{mol O}_2 (\text{mg Chl h})^{-1}$ (Fig. 2, kinetics 1). $[\text{CuL}_2]\text{Br}_2$ inhibits oxygen release in a concentration-dependent manner. At concentrations of $3 \mu\text{M}$ (2), $20 \mu\text{M}$ (3), $50 \mu\text{M}$ (4), and $100 \mu\text{M}$, the reaction rates are reduced by approximately 15%, 43%, 59%, and 69% compared with the control (100%). (Fig. 1, kinetics 2-5).

Information on the localization of the inhibition site of this inhibitor in PSII and on possible mechanisms of inhibitor action can be obtained by photoinduced changes in the fluorescence yield of chlorophyll PSII associated with photoreduction of the primary quinone

electron acceptor, Q_A , including the use of exogenous electron donors (acceptors) and/or known inhibitors with well-studied effects on PSII. The results of these studies are shown in Fig. 3.

In the presence of $[\text{CuL}_2]\text{Br}_2$, there is a significant decrease in F_M level (kinetics 2), and this decrease in F_M level is greater at higher concentrations of added $[\text{CuL}_2]\text{Br}_2$ (kinetics 3 and 4). $[\text{CuL}_2]\text{Br}_2$ causes no change in the F_0 level (neither increase nor decrease) (kinetics 2-4). The inhibition of photoinduced F_V PSII is 66%, 48%, and 32% at $[\text{CuL}_2]\text{Br}_2$ concentrations of $8 \mu\text{M}$ (kinetics 2), $30 \mu\text{M}$ (kinetics 3), and $100 \mu\text{M}$ (kinetics 4), respectively. These data are in good agreement with those obtained in experiments on photosynthetic oxygen release (Fig. 2). Exogenous electron donors (sodium ascorbate, DFC, Mn^{2+}) did not block the inhibitory effect of $[\text{CuL}_2]\text{Br}_2$ on F_V , regardless of the sequence of addition of these reagents (not shown). Moreover, the degree of F_V suppression by the same concentration of $[\text{CuL}_2]\text{Br}_2$ did not increase with increasing incubation time (3 and 21 min) in the presence of this inhibitor in the dark (not shown).

DISCUSSION

The fact that there is no photosynthetic oxygen evolution by PSII-membranes observed in the absence of artificial electron acceptors (AEA), but in the presence of the studied agent at a concentration of 0.1 mM (Figure 2, kinetics 6), it can be concluded that the studied agent $[\text{CuL}_2]\text{Br}_2$ (or, for example, its putative oxidized form), obviously, is not able to act as an exogenous PSII electron acceptor.

A decrease in the photosynthetic oxygen evolution rate by PSII membranes in the presence of exogenous electron acceptors is observed if $[\text{CuL}_2]\text{Br}_2$ is present in the measurement medium; it may indicate that $[\text{CuL}_2]\text{Br}_2$ inhibits the functional activity of some PSII electron transport chain components. However, it can also be assumed that this observed effect is the result of a direct chemical interaction between AEA-s and $[\text{CuL}_2]\text{Br}_2$ (for example, oxidation of AEA-s by $[\text{CuL}_2]\text{Br}_2$) leading to the depletion of AEA-s concentrations and, as a consequence, to the decrease in the rate of oxygen evolution. However, the following experimental fact testifies against this assumption: (1) The absence of changes in the absorption spectra of both used AEA-s and $[\text{CuL}_2]\text{Br}_2$ upon mixing and co-incubation for a sufficient time under the conditions of measuring the photosynthetic oxygen evolution rate but in the absence of PSII membranes (not shown); (2) $[\text{CuL}_2]\text{Br}_2$ does not have any absorption bands in the red region of the spectrum ($\lambda > 650$ nm) (not shown). Therefore, a $[\text{CuL}_2]\text{Br}_2$ concentration-dependent decrease in the rate of the photosynthetic oxygen evolution also is not a result of both either direct chemical interaction between AEA-s or $[\text{CuL}_2]\text{Br}_2$ the actinic light screening by $[\text{CuL}_2]\text{Br}_2$.

It can be assumed that $[\text{CuL}_2]\text{Br}_2$ acts as an exogenous electron donor capable of competing with the endogenous OEC for positive equivalents from RC and, therefore, for the ability to supply electrons for the reduction of the DCBQ + FeCN pair, however not directly as a result of a direct chemical reaction, but through the components RC. This could be manifested as a decrease in the rate of light-induced oxygen evolution with an increase in the concentration of $[\text{CuL}_2]\text{Br}_2$. However, the above indirect data on the redox properties of Cu^{2+} aqua ions and the effect of organic ligands on them makes this assumption unlikely. The fact that the degree of inhibition of the photosynthetic oxygen evolution rate by PSII-membranes does not depend on the time of incubation in the presence of $[\text{CuL}_2]\text{Br}_2$ in the dark (effect measured after 3 minutes is equal to that after 21 minutes) indicates that $[\text{CuL}_2]\text{Br}_2$ sufficiently quickly reaches the

target, apparently localized in the hydrophobic region of the PSII pigment-protein complex. This assumption is also supported by the fact that $[\text{CuL}_2]\text{Br}_2$ is very slightly soluble in aqueous media and, therefore, a stock solution of $[\text{CuL}_2]\text{Br}_2$ was prepared in DMSO.

Based on the above reasoning, we are inclined to assume that the decrease in the photosynthetic oxygen evolution rate by PSII membranes observed in the presence of $[\text{CuL}_2]\text{Br}_2$ is the result of inhibition by $[\text{CuL}_2]\text{Br}_2$ of the functional activity of some component of the PSII electron transport chain.

The PSII maximum quantum photochemical yield of the dark-adapted samples $\phi_{\text{Po}} = \text{Fv}/\text{Fm}$ equal to 0.79 ± 0.02 testifies that the photochemical activity of PSII in the used PSII-membranes is rather high and these PSII-membranes can be used to explore $[\text{CuL}_2]\text{Br}_2$ inhibitory effects on PSII. The effective decrease in F_M caused by $[\text{CuL}_2]\text{Br}_2$ may be due to the fact that (a) there no separation and stabilization of charges in the RC occurs; (b) due to the inhibition of the functioning of some component of the OEC, electrons from the OEC through the RC to Q_A are not supplied, which are necessary for the photoaccumulation of the reduced Q_A and, therefore, F_M cannot reach a level as in the control; (c) $[\text{CuL}_2]\text{Br}_2$ acts as an exogenous electron acceptor that removes an electron from Q_A more efficiently than the OEC supplies electrons to Q_A and therefore photoaccumulation of the reduced Q_A does not occur and it is revealed as decrease of F_M . (c) $[\text{CuL}_2]\text{Br}_2$ is a quencher of the excited states of chlorophyll, and this manifests itself as quenching of chlorophyll fluorescence. Let's consider these assumptions in reverse order.

(d) $[\text{CuL}_2]\text{Br}_2$ selectively reduces the intensity of only the variable chlorophyll fluorescence (Fv), and does not affect the level of F_0 (Figure 3). Taking into account the fact that $[\text{CuL}_2]\text{Br}_2$ does not decrease the F_0 level, as well as the absence of any $[\text{CuL}_2]\text{Br}_2$ absorption bands in the range of the chlorophyll fluorescence emission spectrum (not shown), the assumption that $[\text{CuL}_2]\text{Br}_2$ acts as a fluorescence quencher seems unlikely.

(c) If $[\text{CuL}_2]\text{Br}_2$ acted as a very efficient exogenous electron acceptor, then (1) the dark decay of Fv reflecting the rate of reoxidation of reduced Q_A could be greatly accelerated; (2) the photoinduced growth rate of Fm could be decreased; (3) we could observe light-induced oxygen evolution in the absence of exogenous electron acceptors; (4) there could be spectral changes in the absorption spectrum of $[\text{CuL}_2]\text{Br}_2$ indicating the formation of the reduced form of this agent. However, none of the abovementioned occurs (Fig. 2 and Fig. 3). So $[\text{CuL}_2]\text{Br}_2$ does not

act as an electron acceptor.

(b) It could be assumed that $[\text{CuL}_2]\text{Br}_2$ is incorporated somewhere on the donor side or between its components and blocks and/or slows down normal electron donation and/or acts as an exogenous "poor" electron donor to the RC, unable to provide efficient photoaccumulation of reduced Q_A . However, the lack of slowdown in the rate of F_m rise in the presence of $[\text{CuL}_2]\text{Br}_2$ (Figure 3 kinetics 2-4), and especially the inability of exogenous electron donors to overcome the inhibition by $[\text{CuL}_2]\text{Br}_2$ and thus restore F_m to its original level (not shown) is the evidence against the fact that the donor side is the site of the inhibitory action of this agent. In addition, the indirect data on the redox properties of $[\text{CuL}_2]\text{Br}_2$ discussed above also testify against this assumption.

(a) Thus, the main site of the inhibitory effect of $[\text{CuL}_2]\text{Br}_2$ most likely is the components of the PSII reaction center. This assumption is quite convincingly confirmed by all the considerations discussed above, which reject other sites of action of this agent on PSII. In addition, as it was considered in the introduction, the most likely and the most experimentally substantiated main site of action among several auxiliary sites of action of both Cu^{2+} aqua ions and organometallic complexes based on Cu^{2+} seems to be components of the PSII reaction center.

The calculated IC_{50} (30 μM) at a concentration of PSII-membranes of 20 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ chlorophyll is quite comparable with the data obtained by other authors. Value(s) IC_{50} of the PSII oxygen evolution activity inhibition by CuCl_2 (1) in spinach chloroplasts at Chl concentration 20 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ was 18-20 μM (Hsu et al., 1998) in the presence of DCBQ or ferricyanide were respectively 6.6 μM and 20.7 μM at Chl concentration 6.66 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ or 19 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ in PSII-membranes and thylakoids, respectively (Yruela et al., 1991); in PSII-membranes at Chl concentration of 20 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ was 8-10 μM (Renger et al., 1993); in PSII-membranes at Chl concentrations 10 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ was 7 μM (Yruela et al., 2000). Inhibitory activity of diaqua-(N-pyruvidene- β -alaninato) copper(II) monohydrate ($\text{Cu}(\text{pyr}-\beta\text{-ala})$) expressed by the IC_{50} value, as compared with control samples was 136 μM at chlorophyll concentration equal to 30 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ (Sersen et al., 1997). The K_i (16 μM), $-\log K_i$ (4.8) and xt equals one $[\text{CuL}_2]\text{Br}_2$ molecule on one chlorophyll molecule or 220–250 inhibitor molecules per one PSII reaction are different from the data DCMU: 1 DCMU molecule per about 300 molecules of chlorophyll (Tischer et al., 1997; Van Rensen et al., 1978) but comparable with data for a potent inhibitor of photosynthesis 4,6-dinitro-o-

cresol (DNOC): 1 binding site per 2.3 chlorophyll molecules (Van Rensen et al., 1978). Values of K_i for inhibition of oxygen evolution activity by Cu^{2+} aqua ions (as CuCl_2) or DCMU in the presence of 0.5 mM DCBQ as an artificial electron acceptor obtained by Yruela et al in 1992 (Yruela et al., 1991) were 5.88 (5.32) μM and 0.023 μM respectively. As to $[\text{CuL}_2]\text{Br}_2$ binding site, the data that $[\text{CuL}_2]\text{Br}_2$ independently binds with only one binding site per acceptor molecule are similar conclusion that was made for inhibitor, 4,6-dinitro-o-cresol (Van Rensen et al., 1978).

It can be assumed that $[\text{CuL}_2]\text{Br}_2$, incorporated somewhere on the donor side or between its components, blocks and/or slows down normal electron donation and/or acts as an exogenous electron donor for RC, unable to provide efficient photoaccumulation of reduced Q_A . However, the lack of slowing of the growth rate of F_m in the presence of $[\text{CuL}_2]\text{Br}_2$ (Fig. 3, kinetics 2-4), and especially the failure of exogenous electron donors to overcome $[\text{CuL}_2]\text{Br}_2$ inhibition and thereby restore F_m to its original level (not shown), indicates that the donor side is the site of inhibitory action of this agent.

CONCLUSION

According to the purpose of the work, to investigate the possible effects of a new organometallic complex, $[\text{CuL}_2]\text{Br}_2$ PSII, several different interesting effects were identified and studied at the level of different PSII regions. Thus, the main site of the inhibitory action of $[\text{CuL}_2]\text{Br}_2$ is most likely the components of the PSII reaction center. This assumption is quite convincingly confirmed by all the considerations discussed above, rejecting other sites of the action of this agent on PSII. The obtained results can be used in the development of methods for the guaranteed delivery of the active element to the site of its main activity in the organic complex.

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Yeni Cu(II) kompleksinin ispanaq II fotosisteminin fotokimyəvi aktivliyinə təsiri

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Alaq otlarına qarşı mübarizə üçün istifadə olunan müasir vasitələrin böyük bir qrupunun təsir mexanizmi elektron nəqliyyat zəncirinin müəyyən bir hissəsində fotosintezin işıq mərhələsində elektron nəqliyyatının qarşısını almaqdır. Yeni [CuL₂]Br₂ kompleksi (L=bis 4H-1,3,5-triazino [2,1-b] benzotiazol – 2 –amin, 4-(2-imidazol) mis(II) bromid kompleksi) ispanaqdan təcrid olunmuş FSII membranlarının fəaliyyətinə təsiri, fotosintezdə oksigenin ayrılması və FSII-nin birinci xiron elektron akseptoru olan plastoxinon QA-nın fotoreduksiyası ilə əlaqəli FSII fluoresensiya çıxımının (FV) dəyişməsi ilə öyrənilmişdir. Biz görürük ki, [Cl₂]Br₂ FSII-nin fotokimyəvi fəaliyyətini effektiv şəkildə inhibə edir, bunu FSII-nin hər iki xarakterik fotoreaksiyalarının eyni effektivliklə yatırılması sübut edir.[Cl₂]Br₂ FM səviyyəsini azalması yalnız FV səbəbi ilə baş verir; nə F₀ səviyyəsində dəyişikliklərə, nə də fotoinduksiya edilmiş FM artımının yavaşlamasına səbəb olmur. Suni elektron donörleri [Cl₂]Br₂-nin inhibitor təsirini ləğv etmir. Çox güman ki, donör tərəfində və ya onun komponentləri arasında bir yerə daxil olan [CuL₂]Br₂, təbii elektron bağışına maneə törədir və/və ya yavaşladır və/və ya RM üçün ekzogen elektron donör kimi xidmət edir. Beləliklə, FSII reaksiya mərkəzinin komponentləri, böyük ehtimal, [Cl₂]Br₂ inhibitor fəaliyyətinin əsas hədəfidir. Tapıntılar su ionlarının Cu(II) və Cu(II)-üzvi komplekslərin FSII-yə inhibitor təsiri haqqında ədəbiyatlardan əldə olunan məlumatlarla müqayisə olunur.

Açar sözlər: Fotosintetik inhibetləşmə, mis, metalorganik kompleks, fotosistem II, oksigen ayrılması